

DIGITAL PROJECTS ON PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP AND IT'S BENEFITS

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Abstract. *This article includes the benefits of the public-private partnerships and anything of using digital programs for PPP. We took into consideration not just digital projects on PPP, we tried to learn, analyze and make good solutions on the spheres of Healthcare, SDG, and in education system. All decision made by learning many countries experience for using in Uzbekistan. Some projects may not useful for Uzbekistan and we tried to make more suitable ones for the country.*

Keywords: *public-private partnership, Digital projects, Digital healthcare, Benefits of digital solutions, telemedicine.*

Introduction. The integration of digitization into the planning and delivery of infrastructure and services in health, education and long-term social care services is a promising strategy to transform these sectors. Procuring these through a PPP (“Public-Private Partnership”) method leverages the strengths and resources of the public and private sectors, creating partnerships that not only improve service delivery and infrastructure, but also pave the way for achieving the SDGs. In the era of digital transformation, which is fundamentally changing capabilities and opportunities, the opportunities for innovation and sustainability in social sector services cannot be considered great without PPPs. As such, governments around the world are increasingly recognizing the importance of these partnerships in building more robust, efficient and inclusive Social Sector infrastructure and services. In most countries PPPs have emerged as a main mechanism for developing digital social sector infrastructure and services in various sub-sectors, including health, education and other social services. These partnerships represent collaborative efforts between government entities and the private sector to address capacity and capability gaps.

The Covid-19 pandemic has shaped the global community's fight against the virus through innovative digital public-private partnerships (DPPPs) under the backdrop of the 4th industrial revolution. The World Health Organization (WHO) and many countries have launched programs that harness the power of computer technology from Microsoft, Google, Amazon, Facebook and others for innovative interventions in the fight against the pandemic.

Cobb-Douglas production is obtained by linking the production of private technology companies to improve the total return on investment and total production productivity. The new term is proposed to ensure that digital PPPs should continue after the pandemic and maximize their benefits to ensure the desired file.

Public-Private Partnership (PPP) projects provide an opportunity for development of telecommunication infrastructure without placing the full burden of the ultimate financial demands on the public balance sheet. They also allow the operator to spread the cost of infrastructure over time, rather than requiring a considerable up-front capital expenditure.

In developing any country's program or strategy, whatever the project may be, financing, or by referring to a specific place or geographic area in this document, the Asian Development

Bank does not assume any legal or other status of that country. (Technical Assistance Report ADB-2022)

Literature review. The Sustainable Development Goals require the establishment of various partnerships, including PPPs on development programs (Jomo, 2016). But, it was not used until 2016 when the concept of the 4th Industrial Revolution was first raised on the agenda of SDG (Schwab, 2017), innovations on the agenda of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). PPPs are limited in terms of financial support, including the tools aimed at the absorption of resources, mainly aimed at coordinating the national budget, development aid funds, bank funds and charity work to eliminate the financial gap (WB, 2019).

In a sector of using Public-private partnership programs, there are huge lacks of technological resources which will ensure the development of the 4th industrial revolution. On January 30, 2020, the World health organization declared the Covid-19 outbreak - a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC). Experts of the WHO's media titled the paragraph "Critical role of artificial intelligence in the fight against the virus" which tell about the disease. (Mariano Jr. & Wu, 2020).

Mariano and Wu studied the key role of technology in fighting against pandemic on the paper called "Opens a window on the field of technology" (Mariano Jr&Wu, 2020). Thus, a number of collaborations with WHO and Tech Giants including Microsoft, Google, Amazon, Facebook, etc. have been piloted to address the challenges of early detection and warning, pandemic control, and public awareness for disease surveillance and prevention. (WHO, 2021).

Research methodology. The article was researched based on analysis and comparison methods. The causes, alleles and comparison of statistical materials and scientific observation, comparative analysis, induction and deduction methods were considered in the development of the free will of the PPP.

Analysis.

Digitization of health requires a multifaceted strategy that includes surveillance, government regulation, corporate responsibility, and public awareness in mitigating social ills, along with a single benefit system. A PPP structure provides an established mechanism by which privileges, rules and norms, specific functions and responsibilities can be delineated and distributed to achieve beneficial outcomes.

According to The Economist, if each country reaches the level affected by the Spanish flu pandemic, GDP could shrink by as much as 5% and there is a risk that part of the global economic forecast for 2020 will be lost.

Global GDP growth forecast for the near future.
Source: S&P International Agency.

S&P agency forecasts that world GDP declined by 2.4% in 2020 compared to the previous year. According to the analysis of the international agency S&P, economic growth reached 5.9% in 2021 and 3.9% in 2022.

The consumer price index in Uzbekistan rose by 1.7% in April. In April 2019, it increased by 0.9%. In turn, food prices rose by 3.3% compared to the previous year, non-food prices by 0.7% and services by 0.3%.

In the rest of the world, the consumer price index in April fell by 1.5% in the United States, 4.3% in China, 2.5% in Russia, 2.3% in Iceland, 9.5% in Pakistan and 0.6% in Belgium. In Egypt, it increased by 10%.

It can be concluded that inflation is higher than in developed countries and in countries where the economy is currently dependent on tourism or transport. As a result, the country's demand for consumer goods has fallen sharply, leading to the breakdown of some economic sectors and services. In the current crisis, it is necessary to intensify the process of local production of food and raw materials. For this reason, it is important to focus on these areas, whether large or small, to attract investment.

There are a lot of types of making PPP contracts in sphere healthcare. In addition to contracts for construction, equipment and facilities management, there are contracts for the use of remote resources (outsourcing), investments, joint financing, coordination of joint projects for medical services. The most famous models of PPP are BOLT (Built-operate-lease-transfer) and Spanish public private partnerships: The ‘Alzira model’. The last model-consortium (private) hospital, which is a well-known world model, collects annual fees from the state budget based on the number of visitors (citizens) [1].

Table-1.

Financing of the digital healthcare system in the EU countries with public-private partnership projects.

N	Countries	Total financing (%)	N	Global e-commerce during the years 2017-2023	
1.	Germany	1%	1.	2017	\$ 2.382 mln
2.	Ireland	1%	2.	2018	\$ 2.928 mln
3.	Nederland	3%	3.	2019	\$ 3.535mln
4.	Italy	5%	4.	2020	\$ 4.206 mln
5.	Spain	8%	5.	2021	\$ 4.927 mln
6.	Greece	10%	6.	2022	\$ 5.695 mln
7.	Portugal	19%	7.	2023	\$ 6.542 mln
8.	Denmark	25%			
9.	Switzerland	25%			
10.	Greet Britain	28%			

Source: Authors work.

In Austria, a contractual scheme of cooperation for the sterilization of medical devices was implemented, which led to the creation of a single sterilization Center. It is worth mentioning the PPP in the field of nutrition for hospitals. The need to optimize and rationalize food preparation for hospitals led to contracts for cooking in German clinics such as the "Charité Campus Clinic Virchow", which led to low-cost and high-quality products.

The economics of digitization is the field of economics that studies how digitization, digitalization and digital transformation affects markets and how digital data can be used to study economics. In the world new value creation over the next 5 years will come from digitally enabled platforms. The size and growth of the digital economy was measured by Forrester's new Global Digital Economy Forecast. There are top six digital economies by size the US, China, the UK, Japan, Germany, and South Korea. The digital economy will show the growth 6.9% from 2023 to 2028, and it is growing faster than global GDP. The Global Digital Economy Will Reach \$16.5 Trillion And Capture 17% Of Global GDP By 2028 [2].

Notes: East Asia and Pacific (EAP), Europe and Central Asia (ECA), Latin America and Caribbean (LAC), Middle East and North Africa (MNA), South Asia (SAR), Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA).

Figure -1. Share investments in digital solutions quadrupled in EAP

Source: World Bank

While companies in high-income countries continue to integrate digital solutions to streamline processes and improve efficiency, many companies in low- and middle-income countries were without a computer or internet connection in 2022, particularly small and medium enterprises.

From April 2020 to December 2022, the percentage of micro firms (zero to four employees) investing in digital solutions doubled from 10 percent to 20 percent but for large firms (more than 100 employees) it tripled from 20 percent to 60 percent. East Asia has been the front runner among developing regions, with the share of firms investing in digital solutions quadrupling from 13 percent to 54 percent between 2020 and 2022. In other regions, less than 30 percent of firms did so by the end of 2022.

The services sector is going much faster than Global GDP growth and some countries economy.

Figure-2. Compound Annual Growth Rate of Value Added and Employment, 2000-2022
Source: Digital Progress and Trends Report 2023.

The information technology (IT) services sector, such as software development and tech consulting, grew twice as fast as the global economy, creating jobs at six times the rate of the global economy. But this phenomenal growth was highly concentrated, with the top six economies – the United States, China, India, Japan, Germany, and United Kingdom - accounting for 70 percent of global value added in IT services.

Figure-2. Compound Annual Growth Rate of Value Added and Employment, 2000-2022
Source: Digital Progress and Trends Report 2023

While the field is dominated by high-income countries, developing countries in the East Asia and Pacific region experienced the fastest growth, with export values expanding by 17 times from 2005 to 2022, largely driven by China. India is most specialized in IT services exports, which contribute to one-third of its total services exports.

According to the results of various studies, the weight of the digital economy in the world economy ranges from 4.5 to 15.5 percent. The United States and the People's Republic of China contribute almost 40% of the value added in the global information and communication technology sector and 75% of the patents related to blockchain technologies.

According to statistics, the share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product in the USA is 10.9%, in China it is 42%, and in India it is 12%. In Uzbekistan, this indicator is slightly more than 2 percent.

Conclusion.

According to the statistics and analyses we can see the number of digital projects of Uzbekistan is mostly concentrate for increasing social infrastructure, and energy use. It shows that

the time which Uzbekistan more paid attention for increasing energy production, most countries invest for digitalization of economy.

Table-1.

Share of Digital economy in GDP by countries

#	Countires	Share of Digital economy (%)
1	USA	11%
2	China [3]	42%
3	India	12%
4	Uzbekistan	2.2%
5	Singapore	17.7%
6	Denmark [4]	9%
7	Indonesia [5]	2.9%

World scientists say that digital technologies will dramatically change more than 50 percent of economic sectors. This vision is based on the fact that information technologies and digital platforms will dramatically change business models, eliminate intermediaries and optimize processes for their efficiency. According to the calculations of the World Bank, a 10% increase in the number of high-speed Internet users can increase the annual GDP from 0.4% to 1.4%. Also, the share of the digital economy in the country's GDP is considered to be an indicator of its importance, which increases by approximately 20 percent annually (in developed countries, this indicator is around 7 percent). If this trend continues, after 10-15 years the share of such an economy in the world GDP will approach 30-40%. As an example of the results of the reforms carried out in our country, we can take the activity of the joint-stock company "Uzbektelecom" [6]. In our country, it is necessary to modernize the electronic government, including the system of providing public services, aimed at simplifying the transition from administrative procedures, improving the quality of life of the population, and improving the investment and business environment. For developing and making easy institutional aspects on doing business, Uzbekistan Government should pay attention more on digitalization and for it government should use public-private partnership program on digitalization.

REFERENCES

1. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)., 2014, OECD Principles for good public governance of Public-Private Partnerships: the role of dedicated PPP units. The Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP).,2007, <https://www.unescap.org/resources/public-privatepartnerships-infrastructure-development-primer>.
2. The World Health Organization is leaning on big tech to navigate the COVID-19 pandemic. https://finance.yahoo.com/news/world-healthorganization-leaning-big163425983.html?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xlLmNvbS8&guce_referre IEEE Computer Society., 2021,
3. Cong Wang, Yifan Lu, 2020. Can economic structural change and transition explain cross-country differences in innovative activity?. Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Volume 159, p.
4. WHO., Fighting infection with information. <https://www.who.int/news-room/featurestories/detail/fighting-infection-with-information> - 2021

5. Technical change and the aggregate production function. The review of Economics and Statistics, 312-320. Delmon, J., 2014, Creating a Framework for Public-Private Partnership (PPP) Programs: A practical guide for decision-makers. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/153101468190188221/pdf/99114-WP-Box393188BPUBLIC-PPP-guide-decision-makers.pdf>.
6. Khayitov, S., Komilov, U., Khujakulov, A. The Role of Digital Economy Among Central Asian Countries' Economy- *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 2024, 14543 LNCS, страницы 205–212
7. Mavluda, A., Fazliddin, C., Saidjon, K.- The Importance of Digitalization in Economic Development of the Government- *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 2024, 14543 LNCS, страницы 196–204
8. aime Alonso-Carrera, Xavier Raurich., Labor mobility, structural change and economic growth. *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 56, 2018, 292-310, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmacro.2018.03.002>.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0164070417303063>
9. Lukas Hardt, John Barrett, Peter G. Taylor, Timothy J. Foxon. What structural change is needed for a post-growth economy: A framework of analysis and empirical evidence. *Ecological Economics*, Volume 179, 2021, 106845, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106845>.
10. Eddy Bekkers, Robert B. Koopman, Carolina Lemos Rêgo. Structural change in the Chinese economy and changing trade relations with the world. *China Economic Review*, Volume 65, 2021, 101573, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chieco.2020.101573>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1043951X2030170X>
11. C. Blanquart, M. Koning (2018).- “The local economic impacts of high-speed railways: Theories and facts.” HAL Id: hal-01859467.<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01859467>
12. C. Blanquart and M. Koning (2017).-“The local economic impacts of high-speed railways: theories and facts.” *Eur. Transp. Res. Rev.* 1-14.
13. Asian Development Bank (ADB).,2008, This Public-Private Partnership (PPP) Handbook. <http://www.adb.org/documents/public-privatepartnership-ppp-handbook>. WHO., 2006,
14. The World Health Organization is leaning on big tech to navigate the COVID-19 pandemic. https://finance.yahoo.com/news/world-healthorganization-leaning-big163425983.html?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0
15. <https://www.forrester.com/blogs/the-global-digital-economy-will-reach-16-5-trillion-and-capture-17-of-global-gdp-by-2028/>
16. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1250092/china-digital-economy-gdp-share/>
17. <https://www.bea.gov/system/files/2020-08/New-Digital-Economy-Estimates-August-2020.pdf>
18. <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/id/Documents/about-deloitte/id-about-dip-edition-2-chapter-4-en-feb2021.pdf>
19. The official website of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan is www.stat.uz/uz